

FAIRSFair

Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe

INFORMATION SHEET

DATA STEWARDS

Persistent identifiers

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The data stewards have a big responsibility in supporting researchers in their use of persistent identifiers as these seldom are part of the researchers expertise, while they still are an essential element of implementing the FAIR principles.

Choosing the right identifiers and PID services requires a good understanding of the aims and priorities of the research community. Granularity, proper levels of documentation and the need for reproducibility during the different stages of the research lifecycle should rather be discussed with the researchers sooner than later.

Persistent identifiers have been discussed and developed within the scientific communities for decades, but there are still differences in how they are understood and implemented. An extensive effort to map this landscape was done in the GEDE consolidated assertions document in 2017. (Wittenburg et al. 2017) Generally there seems to be quite a large consensus that governance, management, practice and cooperation are most important in creating good solutions for persistent identifiers, while the technical aspects are usually solvable once agreement on terms and practice has been achieved.

Recently, the EOSC PID policy defined and discussed some of the important responsibilities and concepts regarding persistent identifiers. The policy states that PIDs should be resolvable, i.e. machine actionable and that the PID metadata should contain only very limited information, called “kernel information”. As the existing services and systems are diverse, defining generic parts is by no means simple. The components listed in the EOSC PID policy are PID schemes and services, and the roles treated are authority, service providers, managers, owners and end users. An organisation might acquire one or several of the different roles.

The data steward should look for existing services and if necessary support a sustainable implementation of PIDs in local solutions.

Support the researcher in finding suitable and interoperable solutions. The data stewards play a very important role in supporting the researchers in finding the best PID solutions to enable FAIR data and scientific reproducibility. While the researchers can often describe their own needs and requirements, they are not necessarily familiar with all services and tools that are available and how they can ensure persistence within and around their research and its outputs. The researcher should be guided in formulating requirements for PID use, and when needed the data stewards should discuss these requirements with the service providers.

Ensure you have good PID policies in place. PIDs management and use should always be well documented and planned. Who is responsible for what and how will coming change be managed?

A PID should be identifiable and user friendly both to human and machine. A persistent identifier generally contains two parts (prefix and suffix), plus an initial namespace that makes it possible to recognize it as a PID and ensure uniqueness. The prefix is usually used by the PID authority and service to manage and control ownership of the PIDs when creating them. The suffix can then be either a hash or other string with or without semantics (the last case is also called *opaque*). In both cases, uniqueness has to be ensured when registering the PID, meaning that there is a guarantee that the same identifier has never been in use anywhere else for another object.

PIDs for research data

PIDs for datasets

Versioning is an important part of research data management. Some datasets are growing or evolving and it should be possible to point with sufficient specificity and integrity to a dataset or data subset. This can easily require complex and costly solutions, so be mindful and listen to the community needs.

Granularity is another aspect that might require some analysis. For every dataset or data collection it is good to assess whether it should only have a high level PID (we refer to this as Shallow FAIR) such as for a whole database or, if it is useful and stable enough for assigning PIDs for individual elements like data points or lines of that data, too (Deep FAIR). A Deep FAIR dataset can have metadata describing separate elements, and would have every element findable and machine accessible.

These two aspects above are both examples of how **relations** within and between dataset need to be taken into account when using PIDs.

Data citation should be supported when feasible also for dynamic data. Research data is sometimes published and managed in databases, where data is published as individual nano publications and search queries might produce compiled datasets, which in turn can be given identifiers. Queries can be stored and given persistent identifiers. This enables good prerequisites for replication and citation. In practice, dynamic and evolving datasets create challenges to implementing the FAIR principles on data. The Schema (2020) gives four alternative ways to cite dynamic datasets, which offer different levels of reproducibility:

1. Cite a specific slice or subset
 - the set of updates to the dataset made during a particular period of time or to a particular area of the dataset
2. Cite a specific snapshot
 - a copy of the entire dataset made at a specific time
3. Cite the continuously updated dataset, but add Access Date and Time to the citation
 - Does not necessarily ensure reproducibility
4. Cite a query, time-stamped for re-execution against a versioned database

The RDA Data Citation working group produced a recommendation on evolving data in 2015. The solution comprises of the following core recommendations:

- **Data Versioning:** For retrieving earlier states of datasets, the data needs to be versioned. Markers shall indicate inserts, updates and deletes of data in the database.
- **Data Timestamping:** Ensure that operations on data are timestamped, i.e. any additions, deletions are marked with a timestamp.

- Data Identification: The data used shall be identified via a PID pointing to a time-stamped query, resolving to a landing page. (Rauber et al. 2015)

Another approach is nanopublication for citing parts of datasets, sometimes referred to as micro attribution. This has been applied in life sciences. According to nanopub.org a nanopublication is a graph with three basic elements:

1. The Assertion: An assertion is a minimal unit of thought, expressing a relationship between two concepts (called the Subject and the Object) using a third concept (called the Predicate).
2. The Provenance: This is metadata providing some context about the assertion. Provenance means, 'how this came to be' and includes the methods that were used to generate the assertion and attribution metadata such as authors, institutions, time-stamps, grants, links to DOIs, URLs about the assertion.
3. The Publication Information: This is metadata about the nanopublication as a whole, and pertains to both the assertion and provenance. Similar to the provenance graph, the Publication Information contains "citation-like" metadata but pertains to the nanopublication and not just the assertion.

PIDs data sources

The RDA Persistent Identification of Instruments working group (PIDINST) has collected use cases for persistent identification of instruments, and aims at aligning the collected metadata, and developing a metadata schema. In July 2019 the schema still contained a placeholder for the PID type as a suitable name for the instrument PID system still needs to be found. Collaboration with DataCite resulted in a mapping of the PIDINST schema with the DataCite schema version 4.3. This opens for using DataCite DOI for instruments. PIDs for instruments might also be offered by larger infrastructures, which themselves should be provided with PIDs. This field is under rapid development.

PIDs can also be assigned to for instance APIs, research sites or infrastructures to help track data provenance. Standards and services for these are under development.

PIDs for actors

Researchers should be encouraged to register an ORCID. For other actors identifiers like RoR, ISNI, LEI or other available identifiers can be used, in https/ format if possible. Also, here development is rapid, but try to choose a sustainable solution and monitor the development and take actions to migrate or enrich your data if necessary.

PIDs for software

PIDs for software are currently offered by at least Software Heritage and Zenodo. Consider the need for preservation measures, documentation and dependencies.

Creating semantic interoperability with PIDs

Data dictionaries

PIDs can play a role in creating machine actionable semantically interoperable data. This means creating semantic artefacts for well defined data types. A Data Type Registry can be used to register for instance:

- A. how variables in a dataset of the form w1, d2, temp, etc., correspond to real world notions of weight, distance, temperature, etc.
- B. the measurement units associated with each of those dimensions, e.g., Kelvin, Celsius, or Fahrenheit in the case of temperature.
- C. how those variables are grouped or packed together in datasets.

Other semantic artefacts

Some ontologies or similar services use PIDs with different granularity, this is a good thing if managed properly. Versioning and machine actionability are good traits. Consider the solutions in a longer time frame. Domain specific services might offer highly relevant semantic artefacts and solutions that differ from shared standards and this must be accepted as the usability of the data might suffer if the community de facto standard is not followed. Rather try to impact the service provider towards implementing shared standards.

When and how to mint PIDs?

A PID is an important way to make a research output findable and possible to cite. Data stewards should of course promote and facilitate PID use. But **a published PID is a promise that will cost money to keep**. If the promise is broken the PID owner, manager and service will all lose trustworthiness, beside the annoyance this causes the end users. Using PIDs should be easy for the end user and reliable regarding integrity to be FAIR.

Usually it is recommended that creating PIDs is done as early as possible in the data lifecycle. This helps reproducibility and provenance tracking. On the other hand, the occurrence of “zombie PIDs”, referring to entities that never actually come into existence or aren’t made available, can be a problem. (Wittenburg et al., 2017) One way to manage the lifecycle could be to use existing non-global identifiers (e.g. those used inside a project) as (parts of) PID

suffixes. This has to be done after carefully evaluating the risks posed by including possible semantics in the PID.

Figure 1. PIDs can be constructed in different ways. It is sometimes possible and useful to include elements of provenance or other IDs from a system or local context, but this should be done mindfully. The other option is to create a new completely opaque suffix. A namespace is always necessary, and the two-tier PID has a proxy layer that ensures machine actionability based on the namespace.

Often it is up to the service owner to decide about the level of opaqueness of the PID. **Maximal opaqueness is often recommended**, in order to prevent the pressure to change the PID when components that are visible in the PID change for the object. An opaque PID also avoids its users to falsely assume that they can always be “constructed” following a recipe. Finally, an opaque PID hides the data type and provenance from the end user. (Wittenburg 2019) This principle optimizes interoperability by requiring every relation to be made explicitly. This is often represented with the hourglass analogy (see figure 2). A disadvantage of opaqueness is that complete opaqueness can make PIDs more difficult to identify for a human user, and impossible to interpret in case of complete failure of the PID system when the link to all related information is deleted.

Figure 2. from Wittenburg (2019) CC-BY-4.0. This model clearly illustrates the goal of minimizing the information carried by the PID itself as a way to gain robustness and persistence. The model assumes great alignment between all parts in the ecosystem to ensure semantic interoperability.

Identifiers.org is one example of a service that builds PIDs with semantics and uses a meta-resolver. Their PIDs consist of an assigned unique prefix, followed by a colon and a provider-designated accession number (prefix:accession). The underlying Central Registry provides a centralized directory of these so-called Compact Identifiers. Resource maintainers can use a Prefix Registration Request form to request a prefix in Identifiers.org for their databases or services. Another example of a PID service, The California Digital Library's service Name to Thing (N2t) uses compact ID for several use cases while also promoting opaque PIDs generated by the Noid servers (Nice Opaque IDs) used by ARK.

Dos

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Don'ts

Just creating new PIDs for every entity, without checking whether these entities already have existing PIDs, will not create interoperable data, only costs. Optimal interoperability requires that the same thing is addressed using the same PID in different contexts. Rather than defining new PIDs for an entity, be it a dataset, a piece of software, or a data type, or any term or item you want to represent, you should always first check whether a PID already exists.

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